

**FROM TEXTS TO TECHNIQUES - PHARMACEUTICAL PREPARATION OF VARNAKA
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ABSTRACT

Varnaka Ghrita^[1] is a classical Ayurvedic medicated ghee formulation mentioned in *Chakradatta* traditionally indicated for enhancing *Varna* (complexion), promoting skin health, and supporting overall vitality. Prepared by processing ghee with selected herbal drugs possessing *Varnya*, *Rasayana* properties, *Varnaka Ghrita* is primarily used in disorders of the skin, discoloration, dryness, and premature aging. The lipid base of *Ghrita* facilitates deeper tissue penetration (*yogavahi* property), improves bioavailability of phytoconstituents, and nourishes *Rasa* and *Rakta dhatus*, which are considered fundamental for healthy skin in *Ayurveda*. Owing to its nourishing, rejuvenative, and complexion-enhancing effects, *Varnaka Ghrita* holds significance in Ayurvedic dermatology and cosmetology, and presents potential scope for integrative research in skin care and wellness.

KEYWORDS: *Varnaka Ghrita*, Complexion, *Malahara*.**INTRODUCTION**

Varnaka Ghrita^[1] is a traditional polyherbal formulation recognized in classical Ayurvedic literature for its therapeutic relevance in the management of various dermatological and systemic conditions. The preparation of *Varnaka Ghrita* involves Preparation of *Ghrita* according to *Sneha Kalpana*^[2] and converting it into *Malahara* which represents a crucial pharmaceutical process, as the quality, efficacy, and safety of the final product depend largely on the selection of raw materials, method of processing to preserve the pharmacological properties of individual ingredients while ensuring their synergistic action.

The pharmaceutical preparation of *Varnaka Ghrita* involves multiple stages, including drying, Pounding, and mixing of *Kalka Dravyas* in specified proportions.

Each step plays a significant role in maintaining uniformity, stability, and therapeutic potency of the formulation. With the growing demand for traditional medicines and the need for quality assurance, scientific documentation of preparation methods has become essential.

This article aims to describe the pharmaceutical preparation of *Varnaka Ghrita*^[1] in a systematic manner, highlighting the materials used and the procedural steps involved. Such documentation not only supports standardization and reproducibility but also bridges traditional Ayurvedic knowledge with contemporary pharmaceutical practices.

MATERIALS AND METHODSFormulation - *Varnaka Ghrita*^[1]

Reference - *Chakradatta*

□ **Ingredients**

Table no. 01: Ingredients of Varnaka Ghrita.

SL NO.	USED AS	INGREDIENT	BOTANICAL/ COMMON NAME	FAMILY
1.	Kalka Dravya	Madhuka	Madhuca longifolia	Sapotaceae
2.		Chandana	Santalum album	Santalaceae
3.		Priyangu	Callicarpa macrophyla	Verbenaceae
4.		Sarshapa	Brassica campestris	Cruciferae
5.		Padmaka	Prunus puddum	Rosaceae
6.		Kaliyaka	Berberis aristata	Berberidaceae
7.		Haridra	Curcuma longa	Zingiberaceae
8.		Lodra	Symplocus	Symplocaceae
9.	Sneha Dravya	Go Ghrita	Ghee	
10.	Drava Dravya	Jala	Water	
11.		Kumkuma	Crocus sativus	Iridaceae
12.		Madhuchista	Bees wax	

□ **Method of Preparation**

- i. All the ingredients from 1- 8 were procured and made into a coarse powder form by pounding in a *Khalva Yantra*.
- ii. These *Churnas* are taken, mixed together and made into a *Kalka* form by adding required quantity of water.
- iii. *Go-ghrita* was taken in a vessel and heated over *Mandagni* till the evaporation of water content, disappearance of foam and sound coming from *Ghrita*.
- iv. The prepared *Kalka* and 16 parts of *Jala* was added to it.
- v. The mixture was boiled until all *Sneha Siddhi Lakshanas*^[3] appeared.
- vi. The *Ghrita* was filtered using cloth.
- vii. The filtered *Ghrita* was taken in a vessel and heated over water in double boiling method.
- viii. 1/4 parts of *Kumkuma* was taken and powdered in a *Khalva Yantra* added with few drops of water and added to the *Ghrita*.
- ix. 1/4 of *Madhuchista* was taken melted and filtered through cloth to remove the impurities present and added to the *Ghrita*.
- x. The *Ghrita* was mixed evenly and transferred into an inert container in warm condition.

□ **Precautions taken**

- a) Gloves was worn during the preparation.
- b) The *Ghrita* was filtered while warm to remove residues effectively.
- c) The *Kalka Dravyas* was made into Churna before making a *Kalka*.
- d) Continuous stirring was done to ensure even distribution.
- e) Intensity of fire was maintained throughout.
- f) Filtration was done to remove impurities from *Siktha*.
- g) Transferred to packing bottles before cooling down.

□ **Observations**

- a. On heating, small bubbles and foam were observed.
- b. Characteristic smell was observed.
- c. The *Kalka* obtained perfect wick shape on rolling between 2 fingers after preparation.
- d. On heating, the *Siktha* softened and melted completely.

Fig 01 Churneeekarana Preparation.

Fig 02 - Kalka Dravyas.

Fig 03 - Varnaka Ghrita.

Fig 04 - Paka Stage.

Fig 05 - Kumkuma.

Fig 06 - Varnaka Ghrita.

DISCUSSION

□ **MADHUKA** - *Madhuka* consists of *Madhura-Kashaya Rasa, Guru-Snigdha Guna, Madhura Vipaka, Sheeta Virya, Vata-pitta Shamaka, Kapha Vardhaka*. It possess analgesic action and is indicated in skin conditions, reduces *daha*. It acts as anti-inflammatory - reduces redness, swelling, irritation on skin, Anti oxidant - help protect skin from free radical damage, slowing down ageing process, reducing wrinkles and fine lines. It also possesses moisturizing, wound healing property.

□ **CHANDANA** - Possess *Tikta-Madhura Rasa, Laghu-Rooksha Guna, Sheeta Veerya, Kapha-Pittahara* property. It soothes and has cooling effect - reduce inflammation, redness, ideal for sensitive and inflamed skin. Anti-inflammatory prop - in acne, eczema, psoriasis. Anti-bacterial, antiseptic, moisturises the skin, Brightening and even skin tone - lighten dark spots, blemishes, pigmentation, Antioxidants - help in antiageing, Reduce skin tan, Improve skin texture- soft, smooth, refreshed.

□ **PRIYANGU** - It possess *Tikta-Kashaya-Madhura Rasa, Laghu-Ruksha Guna, Katu vipaka, Sheeta virya, Tridosha hara* property, Healing property - anti microbial and soothing effects, Treats skin disorders, Is Moisturizing, Reduces skin pigmentation, even skin tone, helps in Skin brightening, It is also anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory.

□ **SARSHAPA** - It possess *Katu-Tikta Rasa, Laghu Snigdha Guna, Katu Vipaka, Ushna virya*, It is *Kapha Vata Shamaka, Pittakara*, Anti-inflammatory - reduce inflammation, redness, swelling, irritation, deal for eczema, sensitive and inflamed skin. It has Anti-bacterial and Anti-fungal prop - aid in treating acne and skin infections, exfoliation.

□ **PADMAKA** - It possess *Kashaya-Tikta Rasa, Laghu-Snigdha Guna, Katu Vipaka, Sheeta Virya, Kapha-Pittahara* property, It is Anti-bacterial, Anti-microbial, Anti-inflammatory, Anti-oxidant, Skin Brightening, Healing and soothing, It is moisturizing, reduce skin tan.

□ **KALIYAKA/ DARU-HARIDRA** - It possess *Tikta-Kashaya Rasa, Laghu-Ruksha Guna, Katu Vipaka, Ushna Virya, Kapha Pitta Doshha*. It reduce excess oil on skin - control sebum production, reduce acne and clogged pores. It also soothes skin, Anti-ageing, Detoxify skin, Skin Brightening, Promotes skin healing and also is Anti-bacterial, Anti-Fungal, Anti-inflammatory.

□ **HARIDRA** - It possess *Tikta-Katu Rasa, Ruksha-Laghu Guna, Ushna Virya, Vata-Kapha hara* property. It is known as *Kustahara, Vranahara* (heals wounds), *Vishodini* (natural detoxifier), *Dehavarna Vidhayini* (Improves skin complexion). Also known to remove facial hairs. *Charaka* included it in *Kusthagna Gana*, It is a Brightening agent - gives even skin tone and brightens skin. it also has wound healing and Oil control.

□ **LODRA** - It posses *Kashaya-Tikta Rasa, Laghu-Rooksha Guna, Sheeta Virya, Kapha-pitta hara* property. It helps in reducing acne, blemishes, white and black heads, even promotes wound healing. It has Anti-inflammatory, Astringent property - tighten skin, minimize pore. it helps in Skin reguvenation - aiding in healing of scars and blemishes. It helps in balancing oil production- regulate sebum production and is Antimicrobial, Skin brightening and Cooling in nature - ideal for soothing irritated skin.

□ **KUMKUMA** - It works as Skin Brightening agent - Enhance complexion, reduce pigmentation, dark spots, blemishes, radiant and even skin tone. It is Anti ageing in nature - the crocin and safranal present in it helps fight free radical damage, slow down ageing by reducing fine lines, wrinkles, and sagging. It is anti-inflammatory, Anti-oxidant rich, protect skin from oxidative stress caused from pollution, UV rays thereby preventing premature ageing. It provides even skin tone, improve skin texture, soothes Skin burn.

□ **Go - GHRITA** - It helps moisturize and hydrate. It is rich in antioxidants, soothes and heals, promotes skin glow and detoxify- reduce breakouts and blemishes.

□ **MADHUCHISTA** - It helps to deep moisturize. It possess Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Healing and

repairing properties. It Protects from harsh elements, helps in Natural exfoliation, Improve skin elasticity and helps with acne.

Considering all these properties we can come to the conclusion that *Varnaka Ghrita* is a very good product to be used for improving skin health, complexion and reducing acne marks, dark spots and other skin conditions. There is a reference that *Varnaka Ghrita* is used in *Vali* and *Palitha Nashana* too in *Chakradatta*.^[1]

Acharya Chakradatta opines that regular usage of *Varnaka Ghrita* improves lusture and makes the face glow like moon (*Nishkankendu Bimbham Syat Vilasavati Mukham*).^[1]

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, *Varnaka Ghrita*^[1] is a classical Ayurvedic formulation value for its multi-faceted therapeutic properties, particularly in enhancing complexion, promoting skin health and supporting skin health. Prepared with medicated herbs processed in ghee, it facilitates deep tissue nourishment and effective delivery of herbal constituents due to the yogavahi nature of *Ghrita*.

Even though the name suggests the product to be in *Ghrita* consistency, the final product turned out to be in a semi-solid *Malahara* consistency. This makes it suitable to be used as a cosmetic in regular use.

The ingredients singularly possess various skin related benefits which makes *Varnaka Ghrita* significant in both preventive and curative aspects of Ayurvedic practice, especially in conditions related to skin disorders.

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